

Evaluation of SARS-CoV-2 response at the University of North Carolina (UNC) at Charlotte using percent positivity data and viral genomic sequence data

Daniel Janies^{1,2,3}[0000-0002-7890-9906], Shirish Yasa^{1,2,3}[0000-0003-3217-4921],
Colby T. Ford^{1,3,4}[0000-0002-7859-3622] Jannatul Ferdous^{2,3}[0000-0003-3053-9616],
William Taylor^{2,3}[0009-0000-6204-1172], April Harris^{2,3}[0009-0009-2557-7926],
Sam Kunkleman^{2,3}[0000-0002-2309-6418], Juan Bolanos^{2,3}, Kevin
Lambirth^{2,3}[0000-0002-6568-543X], Denis Jacob
Machado^{1,2,3}[0000-0001-9858-4515], Cynthia Gibas^{1,2,3}[0000-0002-1288-9543], and
Jessica Schlueter^{1,2,3}[0000-0002-6490-0580]

¹ Center for Computational Intelligence to Predict Health and Environmental Risks (CIPHER), University of North Carolina at Charlotte 28223, USA

djanies@charlotte.edu

<https://cipher.charlotte.edu>

² Department of Bioinformatics and Genomics, University of North Carolina at Charlotte 28223, USA <https://cci.charlotte.edu/departments/department-of-bioinformatics-and-genomics/>

³ College of Computing and Informatics, University of North Carolina at Charlotte 28223, USA <https://cci.charlotte.edu>

⁴ School of Data Science, University of North Carolina at Charlotte 28223, USA <https://sds.charlotte.edu>

⁵ Division of Research, University of North Carolina at Charlotte 28223, USA <https://research.charlotte.edu/>

Abstract. In this paper, we use two datasets: 1) percent positivity data based on real-time PCR testing of students on the UNC Charlotte campus and in the surrounding County, Mecklenburg, North Carolina) and 2) nucleotide sequence data from SARS-CoV-2 isolates from students who tested positive and similar background data collected globally and submitted to The National Center for Biotechnology Information, (NCBI-GenBank). We develop graphical and phylogenetic means to assess the disease mitigation efforts over time. These efforts included the early warning of wastewater surveillance, the encouragement of vaccination, intensive testing, contact tracing, and isolation of infected students. Based on the percent positivity data, we conclude that there were periods in which the measured percent positivity of SARS-CoV-2 was worse on campus than in the surrounding county and periods where measured percent positivity was worse throughout the county than on campus. The viral phylogeny based on sequence data shows that there was not a long coherent epidemic on campus. It was impossible to keep the virus from coming on campus. The virus invaded the campus multiple independent times, but each time it did not spread due to the disease mitigation

efforts of the campus. One exception is a large clade of campus cases during the Omicron surge.

Keywords: SARS-CoV-2 · Phylogenetics · real-time PCR testing · Disease Mitigation · wastewater testing · vaccination.

1 Introduction

SARS-CoV-2 emerged in Wuhan, China in late 2019. The first case to test positive in North Carolina was reported on March 3, 2020 [1].

As testing was limited and vaccines were unavailable, the only mitigations available on college campuses were social distancing, online learning, and masking. In-person classes ended March 13, 2020, and resumed at reduced density in the second week of September 2020. UNC Charlotte began testing students for SARS-CoV-2 infection with real-time PCR in the third week of September 2020. Sequencing was attempted from all positive COVID-19 tests collected by the on-campus COVID-19 testing lab from September 25, 2020 to May 6, 2022.

In this report, we detail how we produced a very large viral genomic dataset from sequencing isolates from campus and similarity searching large sequence databases. The computing time to calculate the phylogenies was significant, using over 151 CPU days. Once a heuristically optimal phylogeny was discovered we used a simple technique, the consistency index, [2,3] to assess whether SARS-CoV-2 entered the campus population and consistently spread or entered the campus and spread was dampened each time a small outbreak occurred.

This was time well spent as we demonstrate that multiple layers of disease mitigation including wastewater surveillance, intense disease testing, encouragement of vaccination, isolation, and treatment of infected persons, can abate the severity and persistence of outbreaks of infectious diseases. In other words, we experienced a few outbreaks on campus but not a wide sustained coherent spread of SARS-CoV-2.

Other groups have used viral sequencing to study the epidemiology of SARS-CoV-2 on campus. A group in the United Kingdom (UK) [4] sequenced 482 SARS-CoV-2 isolates from the population of the University of Cambridge (UoC) from October to December 2020. Using phylogenetics this group compared the campus data to 972 sequences from the surrounding community.

Our study is much larger in dataset size and temporal scope with 43,929 total isolates of SARS-CoV-2. Moreover, we collected 1,302 isolates of SARS-CoV-2 for 1 year, 7 months, and 12 days. Ours is the only study to use the consistency index in the context of disease surveillance. There are other important differences due to the lack of a lockdown in North Carolina versus a nationwide lockdown in the UK starting November 5, 2020. The campus population at the UoC was infected early before the national lockdown. Most of the UoC campus infections (70%) were tied to one outbreak [4].

Similarities in the studies include the fact that small outbreaks in the campus populations in the UoC or UNC Charlotte did not cause ongoing coherent epidemics. This result indicates that universities can control epidemics.

2 Methods

Viral genomic data was sequenced using the ARTIC pipeline with the medaka workflow on an Oxford Nanopore PromethION (TM) sequencer [5] from viral isolates collected at UNC Charlotte during the September 25, 2020 to May 6, 2022 timeframe.

Percent positivity data is based on real-time PCR testing of students on campus. Data are not associated with any personal information as specified in the institutional review protocol IRBIS-21-0113 entitled "Enhancing the Value of COVID-19 Campus Environmental Surveillance". The on-campus testing operation was well-resourced and available on-demand to all students and employees, whether living on or off campus. Initially, students underwent testing when: (1) they reported to the Student Health Center with symptoms, or (2) when on-campus contact tracing identified them as a close contact with an infected individual, or (3) at random when selected for testing as part of a cohort during periods of high transmission, or (4) en masse within 24 hours when building wastewater in their residence hall was positive [6]. Testing in the on-campus center was supplemented with testing of student-athletes and high-volume entry and exit testing of students, which were carried out by external providers. Those samples were not made available for sequencing, although the count of positive tests from these supplementary programs is reflected in the on-campus case totals. The majority of outpatient public health testing in Mecklenburg County was carried out by StarMed (<https://starmed.care/>), which operates a regional chain of outpatient clinics. During high transmission periods, StarMed operated a large number of drive-through testing sites throughout Mecklenburg County and surrounding regions. These sites served a variety of citizen needs including symptomatic testing and required testing as a condition of employment or travel.

We calculated the seven-day moving average percent positivity of tests on campus (green) and compared it to similar data compiled and released from the surrounding county (red; Mecklenburg County, North Carolina) during the September 25, 2020 to July 25, 2021 timeframe when the county stopped reporting Figures 1 and 2. We calculated the seven-day moving average in Tableau (tableau.com) which takes the average of the previous 6 days of data + the current day and averages them. We calculated the overall average using the "AVERAGE" function in Excel (microsoft.com).

The background viral genomic data set was built using Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST)[7] searches under default conditions using the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI-GenBank) BLAST interface to the SARS-CoV-2 database or nucleotide database for 1302 on campus isolates and taking 100 highest scoring pairs from each BLAST result. The NCBI-GenBank viral sequence data associated with high-scoring pairs were concatenated and deduplicated by accession number, not sequence content, using the AWK language.

The resulting dataset included 43,929 SARS-CoV-2 sequences drawn from: on campus (n=1302), NCBI-Genbank (n=42,627), and using the original isolate

of SARS-CoV-2 from a human in Wuhan China collected in 2019, as an outgroup (NC045512 from NCBI-Genbank).

These data were aligned using MAFFT under default parameters [8]. The resulting alignment was searched for optimal phylogenetic trees using Tree Search with New Technology (TNT version 1.6 - 64 bits - August 2023); using rseed -; level 1 rep 100 [9]. We used 10 iterations of this search method and found that the optimal tree score was consistently hit.

We used Mesquite version 3.7 (build 940) to visualize the tree, root on the outgroup, and calculate the consistency index. We used the consistency index as a means to evaluate the nature of the invasion of the SARS-CoV-2 virus to campus. A simplified illustration of how the consistency index was used to evaluate the invasion is provided in Figure 3.

Fig. 1. Seven-day moving average of percent positivity of PCR tests on campus (green) versus the surrounding area (red, Mecklenburg County, North Carolina) in the time-frame 9/25/2020 to 7/25/2021.

We created a binary character for off-campus vs on-campus isolates. We used the Mesquite commands: "trace character history: show tree value using character matrix: consistency index for matrix".

3 Results

3.1 Percent Positive Data

The seven-day moving average for percent positivity on campus versus similar data for Mecklenburg County, North Carolina is presented in Figure 1.

The results of the comparison of the percent positivity of testing data on campus versus the surrounding county show three patterns. First, in the period October 2020 to February 2021, UNC Charlotte had a higher percent positivity of testing for SARS-CoV-2 than the surrounding county. Second, from February 2021 to July 2021, UNC Charlotte had a lower percent positivity of testing for SARS-CoV-2 than the surrounding county. Third, in the period July 2021 to

Fig. 2. A map of Mecklenburg County, North Carolina (outlined in black). The city of Charlotte is in red. UNC Charlotte is indicated by the green dot (used under a GNU Free Documentation License).

Consistency index (CI) for invasion of SARS-CoV-2 on campus
(range 0 to 1)

- CI close to 0 is multiple invasions
- CI close to 1 is a ongoing campus outbreak

Fig. 3. Simplified illustration of the use of the consistency index to measure various scenarios for the transmission and spread of the SARS-CoV-2 virus to campus. Red branches are on campus isolates. Black branches are off-campus isolates. The scenario on the left is what we find in our analyses as a low consistency index. The virus invaded campus multiple independent times but was stopped each time and did not spread in a large coherent outbreak. The scenario on the right represents a putative result with a high consistency index that we did not find in our results. In this putative result, the virus invades campus and spreads as a coherent clade that spreads unabatedly

August 2021, the campus had a higher percent positivity of testing for SARS-CoV-2 than the surrounding county.

3.2 SARS-CoV-2 Nucleotide Data

The multiple sequence alignment for the nucleotide data had 29183 aligned positions. The tree search of the nucleotide data consistently hit 42345 steps. The consistency index of the off-campus vs on-campus isolate character was 0.00098135. The length of the off-campus vs on-campus isolate character was 1019 steps. All raw data and the final tree are posted in a public repository

<https://zenodo.org/records/13630080>.

We scanned the tree for clades of campus isolates. We find clades of many small groups with 1-9 sequences. We focused on medium and larger clades. These medium-sized clades include 8 clades with 10 or more campus isolates. The medium-sized clades contained the following variants: B.1.2, B.1.1.329, Alpha (B.1.1.7), Delta (B.1.617.2), Omicron (B.1.1.529). The only large clade contained 109 campus isolates of Omicron (B.1.1.529).

4 Discussion

4.1 Percent Positive Results

The overall average for Mecklenburg County percent positive SARS-CoV-2 cases between September 25, 2020 and July 25, 2024 was 7.16 %. The average percent positive score for testing for the UNC Charlotte campus in the same timeframe was 9.52 %.

However, these metrics had variability over time. The first period, in which UNC Charlotte had a higher percent positivity of testing than the surrounding county was in the period before vaccines were available to young people in the United States.

In the second period, spring and summer of 2021, vaccines became available to young people [10]. Moreover, the UNC Charlotte spring semester ended with exams on May 13, 2021. After this date, the campus experiences a much smaller population. These factors likely contributed greatly to the reduction of the percent positivity of testing of SARS-CoV-2 on campus relative to the surrounding county observed in the second period.

In the third period, late summer 2021, in which the percent positivity of SARS-CoV-2 tests on campus was higher than in the surrounding county, this result can likely be attributed to two factors. This third period coincided with the SARS-CoV-2 Delta variant wave of infections. The infections in this period occurred in both vaccinated (i.e. breakthrough) and unvaccinated patients. Moreover, in August of 2023, UNC Charlotte began the fall semester in which a full enrollment of students arrived on campus.

Overall, when percent positivity is higher it can also reflect the intensity of testing strategies. For example, testing was mandatory on campus for many students (e.g., athletes and the unvaccinated) but testing was not mandatory for citizens in the surrounding county.

4.2 SARS-CoV-2 Nucleotide Results

A consistency index approaching 1 would mean that there was one viral lineage imported to campus and the subsequent viral lineages are all descendent of that lineage. In essence, with CI approaching 1, this indicates the virus invaded the campus and spread unchecked as one coherent outbreak. **We do not see this pattern.**

A consistency index $\ll 1$ indicates viral lineages are independently imported to campus, and do not spread. This is the pattern we see with a vanishingly low consistency index.

The fact that the clades were mostly small is another reflection of this same phenomenon. The only large clade was during the Omicron surge which is to be expected as Omicron created unprecedented numbers of cases everywhere.

Except for the Omicron event, these result indicates that the campus did not have a local epidemic. This result can be attributed to the many forms of infection mitigation used by the UNC Charlotte campus. We kept UNC Charlotte open with mitigations.

We were not subject to a hard lockdown in the State of North Carolina. Thus, it was not possible to prevent the student population from contracting SARS-CoV-2 outside the campus and bringing the virus to campus.

The early warning of wastewater surveillance combined with the encouragement of vaccination, high-intensity testing, contract tracing, and isolation of infected students, allowed the UNC Charlotte Charlotte to repeatedly stamp out what could have been outbreaks that persisted on campus.

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